

Non-modal analysis of linear multigrid schemes for the high-order Flux Reconstruction method

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ABSTRACT

We present a numerical analysis of linear multigrid operators for the high-order Flux Reconstruction method. The non-modal analysis is used to assess the short-term numerical dissipation in the context of 1D and 2D linear convection-diffusion. The effect of several parameters, namely the number of coarse-level iterations, the polynomial order and the combination of h - and p -multigrid is explored in an effort to identify the most efficient configurations. V-cycle p -multigrid is shown to have increased efficiency at higher polynomial orders, and the use of W-cycles and/or hp -multigrid appear to offer additional advantages. The effect of high Péclet numbers and high aspect-ratio cells is also explored in 2D, and both factors are shown to decrease the error dissipation. Finally, we relate the non-modal dissipation to the convergence rate of the multigrid in a series of manufactured solutions.

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1. Introduction

In Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD), the use of low-order methods is widespread due to their well-known robustness, flexibility and reliability. Having progressed considerably over the last decades, they nowadays provide satisfactory solutions for many flow problems at the industrial level. As scale-resolving simulations gain strategic importance to the CFD industry [1], present-generation methods face known challenges in which high-order methods (HOM) become the subject of growing interest. These challenges include vortex-dominated flows in external aerodynamics, turbomachinery and aeroacoustics. HOM are known to offer superior accuracy for the same computational cost as low-order methods [2], including turbulent simulations [3]. As a result, significant efforts are being made to bring high-order methods into the industrial world, e.g. through the *International Workshops on High-Order CFD Methods* (HIOCFD) [4], the EU-funded *Towards Industrial LES/DNS in Aeronautics* (TILDA) project [5] or the *Advanced High-Order Simulation Methods for Industrial Applications* (ASIMIA) project [6].

A great number of high-order methods have been developed throughout the years, coming from the either finite volume (FV), finite differences (FD) or finite elements (FE). Although (HO) FD methods are comparatively easy to formulate, they lack the geometrical flexibility of FV and FE and therefore the latter are preferred in the high-order context. Essentially Non-Oscillatory Methods (ENO, [7]) and Weighted Essentially Non-Oscillatory (WENO, [8]) are the principal unstructured HO FV methods, while discontinuous Galerkin (DG, [9]) and spectral difference (SD, [10]) are the most popular ones belonging to the FE group.

The Flux Reconstruction (FR) approach is a relatively new method, originally introduced by Huynh to solve linear advection [11] and diffusion [12] problems in 1D as well as 2D quadrilaterals. Aside from a simpler formulation and an easier implementation than previously existing approaches, it came out as a general framework capable of bridging p -type methods such as DG and SD [11]. It was nevertheless proved in [13] that neither can FR fully encompass DG, nor the inverse is possible. The work of Huynh was extended by Vincent, Castonguay and Jameson [14,15] by presenting the family of so-called Energy-Stable Flux Reconstruction (ESFR) schemes, also known as the Vincent-Castonguay-Jameson-Huynh (VCJH) schemes. The ESFR schemes are parametrized by scalar quantities for which certain values allow to recover schemes with different properties. The linear stability for advection-diffusion at all orders was demonstrated in [16], and the FR method was successfully extended to triangles [17–19] and tetrahedra [20]. At the same time, the generality of the ESFR family was exploited to minimize numerical errors, obtaining new schemes in the process [21]. An FR application to compressible Navier-Stokes was reported in [22], while some work was done in terms of reducing aliasing errors for nonlinear conservation laws [23]. The FR method has also received attention due to its ability to simulate turbulent flows by means of implicit LES [24–27].

The numerical analysis of Flux Reconstruction has been the subject of a number of publications. Huynh [11,12] had focused on the stability limits for linear advection and diffusion, and the dispersion and dissipation properties *via* von Neumann analysis have been explored, with good experimental agreement, in [28–31]. Nonlinear stability has likewise been discussed in [32]. An assessment of the ESFR properties for implicit LES has been made in [33], and a similar study by means of spatial eigen-analysis has been performed by Mengaldo *et al.* [34]. Results of numerical analyses of nodal DG methods [35,36] and spectral difference [37] are also often applicable to the FR approach due to its generality. Recently, Alhawary and Wang [38] performed a comparative study between DG and other finite difference methods in terms of dispersion and dissipation properties. Much like the aforementioned papers, they applied the von Neumann analysis and illustrated its

limitation for the assessment of high-order schemes. This limitation lies in the distinction made in the literature between the primary (physical) eigenmode of the numerical scheme and the remaining ones, which are called secondary or spurious. However, it has been shown that in the high-wavenumber range all eigenmodes could contribute in similar proportions to the numerical behaviour of the system. To overcome this issue, they proposed a combined-mode analysis [39] to extract a single dispersion/dissipation curve based on the energy contribution of each eigenmode. Similarly, Fernández *et al.* [40] recently introduced a new technique, the non-modal analysis, to assess the dissipation properties without differentiating between physical or spurious eigenmodes and applied it to Hybridized discontinuous Galerkin methods. In doing so, they provided insights into nonlinear instabilities in under-resolved flow simulations at high polynomial orders. Among other features, the non-modal analysis is also applicable to a generic initial condition, which makes it a more general tool than the von Neumann analysis.

The need for convergence acceleration has driven interest into the development of multigrid methods for almost five decades now. In 1973, Achi Brandt first introduced a Multi-Level Adaptive Technique (MLAT) for the solution of boundary-value problems [41]. The fundamental idea behind the MLAT [42–44] is that conventional iterative methods, like Gauss-Seidel, only damp efficiently the high-frequency components of the errors, whose wavelength is comparable to the grid resolution. Smooth errors, however, decay very slowly. Hence, if one projects the original problem into successively coarser grids and performs smoothing iterations there, the whole frequency spectrum is effectively damped with significant increases in the convergence rate. While the MLAT encompasses two fundamental ideas [45] – adaptive discretization and the multigrid method – it is the latter denomination that has become most widespread with time, so has the method itself gained enormous popularity. Applications to fluid dynamics were reported several years later for incompressible viscous flows [46], inviscid flows [47] and potential flows [48] in FV and FD discretisations. The use of multigrid in FE methods was equally explored in [49]. Later, Brandt’s *Guide to Multigrid Development* [50] collected principles and implementation of this new technique for linear and nonlinear systems of equation, and another monograph [51] covered applications to the resolution of fluid flows. Alongside theoretical developments like the algebraic multigrid [52,53], the method was implemented on unstructured meshes by Löhner and Morgan [54] and Mavriplis [55], whose profuse work tackles inviscid and viscous flows in 2D and 3D mixed-element meshes [56–60].

Rønquist and Patera’s results [61] mark a new stage in the coupling of multigrid techniques with p -type FE methods, although previous literature exists [62,63]. The original multigrid method, based upon the use of several meshes, was referred to as h -multigrid and a new, p -multigrid was proposed [64,65] in which lower polynomial orders act as coarser levels. The majority of applications targeted the simulation of fluid flows using Discontinuous Galerkin methods [66–72]. Given the very reduced numerical dissipation of high-order methods, the p -multigrid proved to be especially useful in damping low-frequency errors and allowed for convergence rates independent of the polynomial order. However, the h -independent convergence rate that characterized h -multigrid was lost, and that was the main motivation for Nastase and Mavriplis [73] to develop combined hp -multigrid methods, also found in [74–77]. Since then, several contributions have been made including implicit p -multigrid [78,79], p -multigrid with static condensation [80], multigrid for high-order Reynolds-Averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS) simulations [81], as well as coupling with hybridizable discontinuous Galerkin [82,83] and continuous Galerkin [84]. The application of hp -multigrid to the Flux Reconstruction method has likewise been reported in [85,86,26], albeit to a much smaller extent.

h -multigrid methods have been thoroughly analysed in the literature, see for example [87–89] and the references therein, where the von Neumann analysis has been consistently applied to the two-level multigrid in order to obtain the amplification factors and theoretical convergence rates. The influence of the Reynolds number and high-aspect ratio cells has also attracted attention [90–93], being both factors of particular interest to flow simulations. The convergence rate was shown to deteriorate for small viscosities, when the relative importance of convection is large, and its relation to suboptimal coarse-grid corrections was pointed out in [91]. High-aspect ratios were likewise identified as problematic, but were successfully dealt with by using techniques such as implicit residual smoothing [93]. Examples of the analysis of p - and hp -multigrid methods are scarcer and can be found in [94–96], again for a two-level multigrid. The focus is mainly on the different types of smoothers available, e.g. Gauss-Seidel, Richardson or Jacobi-type ones, and on the influence of the prolongation and restriction matrices in the multigrid performance. Although there is no consensus as to which smoother is more efficient, line Gauss-Seidel iterators were shown to be particularly adequate at high aspect-ratios [71]. Antonietti *et al.* [97] performed a systematic study of the multigrid performance with DG for higher polynomial orders. The multigrid was applied to a Poisson problem in 2D, and the number of smoothing steps was considered constant at all refinement levels. The authors concluded that the convergence rate worsened as the polynomial order increased. However, the p -independent convergence rate could be retrieved by increasing the number of coarse-level smoothing steps over a certain limit.

While the convergence properties have been the main focus of the aforementioned publications, little attention has been paid to the influence of the multigrid parameters themselves, i.e. the number of coarse-level smoothing steps, the type of cycle (V/W), or the number of h -multigrid levels added to the p -multigrid in a combined hp -hierarchy. Aside from [97], analyses on the behaviour of the multigrid operator *as a whole* are scarce for more than two p -levels. Likewise, there is not enough information on the hp -multigrid performance in the presence of convection, nor in high aspect-ratio meshes.

High-order methods for industrial applications require robust and efficient algorithms, for which numerical analysis can provide relevant *a priori* estimations. In this work we propose to apply the non-modal analysis introduced by Fernández *et al.* [40] to several p - and hp -multigrid operators for Flux Reconstruction discretizations of the linear convection-diffusion equation. Our aim is to find those realistic – as opposed to simplified – multigrid configurations that exploit the potential

of the method and at the same time are robust enough to be applicable in a wider range of problems – from pure diffusion to high-Péclet convection. To that end, this manuscript is organized as follows. The Flux Reconstruction method for linear equations is summarized in section 2, together with the local form of the operators required for a stability analysis. In section 3, we explain the p - and hp -multigrid methods for Flux Reconstruction and section 4 describes the analysis tools used in this study. A discussion of the results for 1D follows in section 5.1, and the extension to 2D is made in section 5.3. Finally, the analysis is linked to simulation results in a series of manufactured solutions from [98] in section 6, followed by a summary of the key findings in section 7.

2. Discretization of the linear convection-diffusion equation

The linear convection-diffusion equation (LCDE) with coefficients \mathbf{a} and $\nu \geq 0$ for a scalar quantity $u(\mathbf{x}, t)$ reads:

$$\frac{\partial u}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\mathbf{F}^{\text{cnv}} + \mathbf{F}^{\text{diff}}) = 0, \quad (1)$$

where the convective (inviscid) flux is $\mathbf{F}^{\text{cnv}} = \mathbf{a}u$ and the diffusive (viscous) flux is $\mathbf{F}^{\text{diff}} = -\nu \nabla u$. In an infinite domain, for a complex wave-like initial condition $u(\mathbf{x}, 0) = \exp(i\boldsymbol{\kappa} \cdot \mathbf{x})$ where i is the imaginary unit, the exact solution is given by:

$$u(\mathbf{x}, t) = e^{i\boldsymbol{\kappa} \cdot \mathbf{x}} e^{-(i\mathbf{a} \cdot \boldsymbol{\kappa} + \nu \|\boldsymbol{\kappa}\|^2)t}. \quad (2)$$

In the presence of a non-zero diffusion coefficient, $\nu > 0$, the system evolves towards a zero-steady-state solution.

We now briefly present the FR discretization of the linear convection-diffusion in 1D. For a detailed description of the Flux Reconstruction method, the reader is referred to the literature [11,12].

2.1. Domain decomposition

The computational domain is divided in elements or cells denoted C_j , where j is a unique integer. The center of the element is located at coordinate x_j , and the element width is h_j . As is common practice in Finite Element methods, a reference space is defined where most arithmetical operations take place. The reference space, which is local to each element, is parametrized by coordinate $-1 \leq \xi \leq 1$ and the mapping from physical space to reference space is as follows:

$$\xi(x) = \frac{2}{h_j}(x - x_j), \quad \frac{d\xi}{dx} = \frac{2}{h_j}, \quad \forall x \in C_j. \quad (3)$$

Inside element C_j , the solution is approximated at a set of $P + 1$ quadrature points (solution points) ξ_k , $k = 0, \dots, P$, locally defining a polynomial of order P . The polynomial can be represented by a vector of modal coefficients $\hat{\mathbf{u}}_j$ of a Legendre basis, or a vector of nodal coefficients \mathbf{u}_j . The latter corresponds to the solution values at the aforementioned quadrature points.

2.2. Spatial discretization

In Flux Reconstruction, the divergence of the fluxes is evaluated in 7 steps.

1. Interpolation of the solution at the cell interface points. In 1D, these are the cell boundaries given by $\xi = \pm 1$. In essence, we can obtain the interpolated values at the left boundary (L) and the right boundary (R) by means of row vectors \mathbf{l}_j^\top and \mathbf{r}_j^\top :

$$u_j^L = \mathbf{l}_j^\top \mathbf{u}_j, \quad u_j^R = \mathbf{r}_j^\top \mathbf{u}_j. \quad (4)$$

2. Computation of the common solution values. At the interface points, a common value for the solution must be defined in order to account for the interaction between neighbouring elements. In this study, the common solution values are calculated using the Local Discontinuous Galerkin (LDG) approach [99]:

$$u_j^{L,L} = \frac{u_{j-1}^R + u_j^L}{2} - \beta(u_{j-1}^R - u_j^L), \quad u_j^{L,R} = \frac{u_j^R + u_{j+1}^L}{2} - \beta(u_j^R - u_{j+1}^L), \quad (5)$$

where β is the upwinding parameter. $\beta = 0$ results in an averaged interface value.

3. Computation of the gradient of the solution, \mathbf{q}_j , as the sum of two components. The first component is the *discontinuous* gradient, which results from directly evaluating the derivative of \mathbf{u}_j . The derivative can be computed by applying a derivative matrix D_j , whose shape is not detailed here (see [100]). The second component is a correction term, proportional to the derivative of certain functions \mathbf{g}^L , \mathbf{g}^R (see [12] for more details) and to the difference between the interpolated solution and the common solution. Hence, \mathbf{q}_j is also called *corrected* (or *continuous*) gradient:

$$\mathbf{q}_j = D_j \mathbf{u}_j + (u_j^{L,L} - u_j^L) \mathbf{g}_j^L + (u_j^{L,R} - u_j^R) \mathbf{g}_j^R. \quad (6)$$

4. Interpolation of the fluxes at the interface points. Taking the left boundary as an example, in the case of linear convection-diffusion with constant coefficients this procedure simplifies to:

$$F_j^{cnv,L} = a \mathbf{l}_j^\top \mathbf{u}_j, \quad F_j^{diff,L} = -\nu \mathbf{l}_j^\top \mathbf{q}_j. \quad (7)$$

5. Computation of the common flux values, for both the convective flux and the diffusive flux, using an appropriate Riemann solver. In this study, we use the Roe scheme for the convective flux, and the LDG scheme for the diffusive flux:

$$F_j^{cnv,L,I} = \frac{F_j^{cnv,L} + F_{j-1}^{cnv,R}}{2} - \frac{|a|}{2}(u_j^L - u_{j-1}^R), \quad (8)$$

$$F_j^{diff,L,I} = \frac{F_j^{diff,L} + F_{j-1}^{diff,R}}{2} + \beta(F_j^{diff,L} - F_{j-1}^{diff,R}) - \tau(u_j^L - u_{j-1}^R), \quad (9)$$

where τ is an optional penalty parameter used to increase stability at the cost of some additional numerical diffusion.

6. Divergence of the corrected fluxes. Similar to step 3, we add the corrections and the discontinuous fluxes, which are evaluated directly from the solution and the solution gradient, to obtain the corrected fluxes. In practice, however, we compute directly the divergence of the fluxes by applying the derivative matrix and by using the derivative of the correction functions, \mathbf{g}'_j^R and \mathbf{g}'_j^R :

$$\partial_\xi(\mathbf{F}_j^{cnv}) = D_j(a \mathbf{u}_j) + (F_j^{cnv,L,I} - F_j^{cnv,L}) \mathbf{g}'_j^L + (F_j^{cnv,R,I} - F_j^{cnv,R}) \mathbf{g}'_j^R, \quad (10)$$

$$\partial_\xi(\mathbf{F}_j^{diff}) = D_j(-\nu \mathbf{q}_j) + (F_j^{diff,L,I} - F_j^{diff,L}) \mathbf{g}'_j^L + (F_j^{diff,R,I} - F_j^{diff,R}) \mathbf{g}'_j^R. \quad (11)$$

7. Transformation to physical space and evaluation of the time derivative. In step 6 we have computed the flux divergence in reference space. To transform it back to physical space, we make use of the Jacobian of the transformation (cf. equation (3)):

$$\frac{d\mathbf{u}_j}{dt} = -\frac{d\xi}{dx} \frac{\partial}{\partial \xi} (\mathbf{F}_j^{cnv} + \mathbf{F}_j^{diff}). \quad (12)$$

This completes the spatial discretization. Clearly, the above steps can be grouped in a compact matrix-operator form as follows:

$$\frac{d\mathbf{u}_j}{dt} = \sum_{i=j-2}^{j+2} \mathcal{A}_{j,i} \mathbf{u}_i, \quad (13)$$

where $\mathcal{A}_{j,i}$ is an operator defined in element C_j acting on neighbouring solution vectors \mathbf{u}_i from cells C_i . In this case, a five-cell stencil is assumed due to the use of the Local Discontinuous Galerkin scheme. In this work, for the LDG flux we choose $\beta = 0$ and a value of τ equal to the diffusion coefficient.

While the above procedure depicts a generic Flux Reconstruction scheme, depending on some choices which still remain open we arrive at various numerical schemes with different properties. Aside from the Riemann solvers, which have already been selected, we may choose:

- Quadrature points: in this work we use Gauss quadrature points. Another common choice is the Gauss-Lobatto quadrature, which includes the element's boundaries.
- Correction functions: the left and right Radau polynomials are used for the right and left boundaries, respectively. In doing so, it can be shown [11] that the resulting scheme is equivalent to a differential formulation of a nodal DG method, therefore being called FR-DG.

2.3. Local form of the spatial discretization

In order to perform a stability analysis, we need to express the spatial discretization as an operator acting only on the local values \mathbf{u}_j , without explicitly making use of neighbouring cells' points. To that end, we assume a periodic initial condition $u(x, 0) = \exp(\iota \kappa x)$ which allows us to write neighbouring values \mathbf{u}_i as linear functions of the local cell values \mathbf{u}_j , for instance $\mathbf{u}_i = \mathcal{T}_{i,j} \mathbf{u}_j$, where $\mathcal{T}_{i,j}$ is a shift matrix. For two adjacent cells, this matrix is diagonal with terms:

$$(\mathcal{T}_{i,j})_{kk} = \exp \left[\iota \kappa \left(\frac{1}{2}(h_i + h_j) + \frac{\xi_k}{2}(h_i - h_j) \right) \right], \quad (14)$$

and reduces to the well-known expression $(\mathcal{T}_{i,j})_{kk} = \exp(\iota \kappa h)$ when $h_j = h_i = h$ (see for instance [38]). We can now express the local discretization operator as follows:

$$\frac{d\mathbf{u}_j}{dt}(t) = \mathcal{A}_j \mathbf{u}_j(t) = \left(\sum_{i=j-2}^{j+2} \mathcal{A}_{j,i} \mathcal{T}_{i,j} \right) \mathbf{u}_j(t). \tag{15}$$

2.4. Time discretization

As per equation (15), we have computed the time derivative of the solution. Equation (15) has the form of a first-order linear system of ODEs and therefore can be integrated exactly by computing the matrix exponential of the operator \mathcal{A}_j :

$$\mathbf{u}_j(t) = \exp(\mathcal{A}_j t) \mathbf{u}_{j,0} \tag{16}$$

Alternatively, one may use a time-discretization technique such as an explicit Runge-Kutta scheme. In such case, if we define the fully discrete operator as the one containing the spatial and temporal discretizations:

$$\mathcal{Z} \equiv \text{fully discrete operator}, \quad \mathbf{u}(t_{n+1}) = \mathcal{Z} \mathbf{u}(t_n), \tag{17}$$

where the time-step is $\Delta t = t_{n+1} - t_n$, then \mathcal{A} and \mathcal{Z} are related by a Runge-Kutta polynomial $\mathcal{P}_S^N(x)$ with S stages that is N -th order accurate in time:

$$\mathcal{Z} = \mathcal{P}_S^N(\Delta t \mathcal{A}). \tag{18}$$

3. Multigrid operators

Let us consider the following linear system where \mathbf{u} is the vector of unknowns:

$$\mathcal{A} \mathbf{u} = \mathbf{f}. \tag{19}$$

For simplicity, we will drop the subscript j from the solution vector. An inexact guess of the solution vector will produce a residual given by $r = \mathbf{f} - \mathcal{A} \mathbf{u}$, which can be damped by applying a generic explicit iterator \mathcal{Z} , in the absence of a forcing term \mathbf{f} , simply as $\mathbf{u}^{(n+1)} = \mathcal{Z} \mathbf{u}^{(n)}$. Conventional iterators like Gauss-Seidel or explicit Runge-Kutta are inefficient at eliminating the low-frequency errors; hence the multigrid is considered as an alternative. The iterative process applying an explicit multigrid operator \mathcal{G} can be written in the same form, $\mathbf{u}^{(n+1)} = \mathcal{G} \mathbf{u}^{(n)} = \mathcal{G}^n \mathbf{u}^{(0)}$, where \mathcal{G} contains all grid-transfer, smoothing and correction operations. We now give some indications on how this matrix is computed.

3.1. Matrix formulation of the V-cycle p -multigrid operator

The linear multigrid algorithm, also called Correction Scheme [50], solves the full system at the fine level and some *residual equations* at the coarse levels. The nonlinear Full Approximation Scheme, commonly used in the Navier-Stokes equations, reduces to the Correction Scheme when applied to linear systems. Using subscript $p = 0, \dots, P$ to denote the level, where P is the finest level and 0 the coarsest one, the working principle of the linear p -multigrid is as follows:

1. Departing from an initial guess $(\mathbf{u}_p)_0^{\text{do}}$, improve the solution of the fine level equation, in this case $\mathcal{A}_p \mathbf{u}_p = \mathbf{0}$. Subscript “do” indicates that this is the initial guess of the *down-cycle* part of the multigrid. A smoother or iterator must be selected for this task, which in this work is restricted to either an explicit Runge-Kutta scheme or a perfect time integration. If one advances m_p times with a time-step Δt , the Runge-Kutta iterator is applied m_p times giving $(\mathbf{u}_p)_{m_p}^{\text{do}} = (\mathcal{Z}_p)^{m_p} (\mathbf{u}_p)_0^{\text{do}}$. For a perfect time-integration, this is simply $(\mathbf{u}_p)_{m_p}^{\text{do}} = \exp(\mathcal{A}_p m_p \Delta t) (\mathbf{u}_p)_0^{\text{do}}$.
2. The fine-level residual $r_p = -\mathcal{A}_p \mathbf{u}_p$ is then computed and restricted down to level $P - 1$ by applying a restriction matrix R_p^{P-1} . This restricted residual is used as forcing term inside the coarse level equation:

$$\mathcal{A}_{P-1} \mathbf{u}_{P-1} = \mathbf{f}_{P-1} = R_p^{P-1} r_p, \tag{20}$$

where \mathcal{A}_p is the spatial discretization operator for the coarse level p . The solution of this system is improved by applying an analogous smoothing step, but accounting for the extra source term. This smoothing-restriction procedure is repeated up to the coarsest level $p = 0$.

3. Once the *down-cycle* part is done, the *up-cycle* part consists of a prolongation of coarser-level solutions and the post-smoothing steps. First, the final guess at some level $p - 1$ is prolonged by means of a prolongation matrix R_{p-1}^p , and added to the previously-obtained guess at level p :

$$(\mathbf{u}_p)_0^{\text{up}} = (\mathbf{u}_p)_{m_p}^{\text{do}} + R_{p-1}^p (\mathbf{u}_{p-1})_{m_{p-1}}^{\text{up}}. \tag{21}$$

4. Then, the corrected solution is smoothed by applying the same smoothing procedure as in the *down-cycle*. In doing so, the solution at level p evolves from $(\mathbf{u}_p)_0^{\text{up}}$ to $(\mathbf{u}_p)_{m_p}^{\text{up}}$. The last two steps are repeated recursively until we reach the finest level, P again.

The above procedure depicts a V-cycle multigrid scheme. Since the fine-level system is homogeneous, one may write the multigrid operator as a matrix acting only on the initial guess, which allows for a numerical analysis of the operator as a whole without need to consider separately the behaviour of the smoothers, the restriction matrices and the prolongation matrices. This can be done independently of the polynomial order and the number of smoothing steps at each level (henceforth referred to as *sweep pattern*).

3.2. Matrix formulation of the W-cycle operator

We only consider W-cycles where the coarse-level loops, henceforth referred to as *w-sweeps*, take place between levels $p = 1$ and $p = 0$. One may easily obtain the matrix operator for a W-cycle multigrid by following the same procedure as in section 3.1 and adding the corresponding extra smoothing operations.

3.3. Matrix formulation of the hp-multigrid operator

The *hp*-multigrid operator needs to be formulated for a set of cells instead of one because of the effective use of coarser meshes with lower *h*-refinement. In general, if H grids are used, the operator must act on 2^{H-1} cells in 1D, or 4^{H-1} in 2D. Fortunately, by virtue of the periodicity of the (wave-like) solution, one may express the p -multigrid part of the cycle using block-diagonal matrices. For instance, a Runge-Kutta smoothing operator $(\mathcal{Z}_p)^{m_p}$ would rather be:

$$(\mathcal{Z}_p)^{m_p,*} = \begin{bmatrix} (\mathcal{Z}_p)^{m_p} & \cdots & \mathbf{0} \\ \vdots & \ddots & \vdots \\ \mathbf{0} & \cdots & (\mathcal{Z}_p)^{m_p} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (22)$$

This applies to all operators, including the restriction and prolongation matrices between p -levels. As for the inter-grid projection matrices, we use a simple averaging for the restriction to a coarser mesh, and pure injection for the prolongation to finer meshes. Remember that the *h*-part of the multigrid happens at constant $P = 0$, therefore there is only one solution point per cell. In a 1D, two-grid case where h_0 is the coarse mesh and h_1 is the fine mesh, this yields:

$$\mathbf{R}_{h_1}^{h_0} = \frac{1}{2} \begin{bmatrix} 1 & 1 \end{bmatrix}, \quad \mathbf{R}_{h_0}^{h_1} = \begin{bmatrix} 1 \\ 1 \end{bmatrix}. \quad (23)$$

At this point, we have the possibility to express in compact matrix form a variety of multigrid operators, with changing number of H and P levels, types of cycle (V and W) and sweep patterns. Moreover, for a fixed multigrid configuration, a number of parameters can still influence the numerical behaviour: the time-step at each level, the mesh characteristics and the ratio of convection to diffusion, among others.

4. Numerical analysis of multigrid operators

4.1. Diffusion properties: non-modal analysis

The procedure for performing a non-modal analysis is similar to a von Neumann analysis in that we seek to write the numerical scheme in matrix form, $\frac{d\mathbf{u}_j}{dt} = \mathcal{A}_j \mathbf{u}_j$. However, instead of analyzing the eigenvalues of \mathcal{A}_j , Fernández *et al.* [40] define a *short-term diffusion* as:

$$\varpi^* := \left(\frac{d \log \|\mathbf{u}_j\|}{d\tau^*} \right)_{\tau^*=0}, \quad (24)$$

where $\varpi^* \leq 0$ is expected, but not required for long-term stability (cf. section 4.3). This quantifies the change in the magnitude of \mathbf{u}_j right after the simulation starts, with τ^* a non-dimensional time. In order to analyze from pure diffusion to pure convection, we select a representative time-scale as:

$$\tau^* = \frac{t}{T}, \quad T = \frac{h_j^*}{\|\mathbf{a}\| + \frac{\nu}{h_j^*}}, \quad (25)$$

recovering the original time-scale from [40] in pure convection cases, $\tau^* = t \|\mathbf{a}\| / h^*$. Note that $h_j^* = h_j / (P + 1)$ is the smallest length scale of the discretization. After some algebra, the above can be rewritten as:

$$\varpi^* = \frac{h_j^*}{\|\mathbf{a}\| + \frac{\nu}{h_j^*}} \mathcal{R}e \left(\frac{(\mathbf{u}_{j,0})^\dagger \mathcal{A}_j \mathbf{u}_{j,0}}{(\mathbf{u}_{j,0})^\dagger \mathbf{u}_{j,0}} \right), \quad (26)$$

where $\mathbf{u}_{j,0}$ is the initial condition, and \dagger denotes the complex conjugate. The former equation provides an explicit expression of the dissipation as a function of the scheme's parameters, in which the contribution of all the operator's eigenmodes

identified in a von Neumann analysis is taken into account. Furthermore, the dispersion curves are symmetric as in the von Neumann analysis; however, they are not periodic.

4.2. Non-modal analysis of a fully discrete operator

Equation (26) evaluates the short-term diffusion from the spatial discretization operator. Alternatively, one may extract the non-modal dissipation curve of a fully discrete (in space and time) operator as follows:

$$\varpi^* \simeq \frac{h_j^*}{\|\mathbf{a}\| + \frac{\nu}{h_j^*}} \operatorname{Re} \left(\frac{1}{\Delta t} \log \left(\frac{(\mathbf{u}_{j,0})^\dagger \mathcal{Z}_j(\Delta t) \mathbf{u}_{j,0}}{(\mathbf{u}_{j,0})^\dagger \mathbf{u}_{j,0}} \right) \right). \quad (27)$$

The fully discrete operator $\mathcal{Z}_j(\Delta t)$ is now a more generic iterator used to advance the solution in time. It may be constructed using an explicit Runge-Kutta scheme, following equation (18), but it also can be a multigrid iterator. In either case, the previous expression will contain a certain amount of temporal dissipation. The temporal dissipation decreases as we approach the time-continuous limit $\Delta t \rightarrow 0$, where time-discretization errors become negligible. Therefore, one can recover the dissipation curve of the spatial discretization operator using equation (27), irrespectively of the explicit Runge-Kutta scheme considered, at sufficiently low values of Δt . This procedure is used in this work to extract the dissipation curves of multigrid operators, while cancelling time-integration errors which often increase the numerical dissipation. A validation of this approximation can be performed using an appropriate tool for symbolic computation. Indeed, using equation (16), one can insert the analytic functions for $\mathbf{u}_{j,p}(t)$ at each level p of the multigrid scheme, obtaining a long analytic expression for the whole cycle, $\mathbf{u}_j(t)$. By symbolic differentiation of equation (24) and evaluation at $t = 0$, we obtain the same curves as in equation (27), although at a much higher computational cost.

4.3. Non-modal dissipation, convergence and long-term stability

In this study, we are interested in solving the steady-state problem $\mathcal{A}_j \mathbf{u}_j = 0$ with a good convergence rate. Knowing that the errors satisfy the same equation as the numerical solution, we relate the efficiency of a multigrid configuration to its non-modal dissipation curve. A multigrid operator with higher short-term diffusion (more negative values of ϖ^*) will dissipate the error-waves faster, therefore having a higher short-term convergence rate.

On the other hand, care should be taken when comparing the short-term dynamics of the system with its asymptotic behaviour. An explicit operator is said to be asymptotically stable when its spectral radius is lower than one, that is, if all the eigenvalues are contained inside the unit circle in the complex plane. This condition guarantees convergence to a stable solution in the long term, at a rate approximated by the magnitude of the largest eigenvalue. However, it is well recognized that the short-term dynamics of a system can significantly differ from the long-term ones. Of particular importance to this study is the fact that positive non-modal damping factors, $\varpi^* > 0$, which imply an initial growth of the solution magnitude, are not necessarily indicative of an unstable scheme in the von Neumann sense. Whenever the eigenvectors of the discrete operator are not orthogonal - which holds in general for this study - a transient increase in the norm of the solution is possible in spite of the solution being a linear combination of exponentially decaying eigenvectors. The differences between short-term and long-term numerical properties of FR schemes constitute an extensive topic by itself which has not been explored in this work; for more details about non-modal stability and the relation between short-term and long-term dynamics, the reader is referred to the work of Peter J. Schmid [101].

5. Results of the non-modal analysis

5.1. 1D diffusion

We first plot the short-term dissipation curves of multigrid operators for the 1D diffusion equation with diffusion coefficient $\nu = 1$. The curves show the damping factor, $\varpi^*(\phi)$, as a function of the normalized wavenumber, $\phi = \kappa h / (P + 1)$. Higher dissipation rates - more negative values for ϖ^* - are expected of the multigrid operator with respect to the spatial discretization operator. As explained in section 4.2, the short-term diffusion of the multigrid operator is evaluated in the time-continuous limit $\Delta t \rightarrow 0$ using equation (27) so that time-discretization errors from the smoothing operations are negligible. Under such condition, we obtain a "pseudo-time-continuous" multigrid which can be compared to the diffusion curve of the corresponding spatial operator \mathcal{A}_p at the finest level, evaluated using equation (26). Note that, any Runge-Kutta smoother could be used without affecting the shape of the curves, provided the time-step remains close enough to zero.

5.1.1. Comparison against von Neumann analysis

In Fig. 1, a comparison is made between non-modal analysis and von Neumann analysis in order to illustrate some similarities and differences. The modal (von Neumann) dissipation curves are computed from the eigenvalues of the operator - see for instance [38], and the so-called physical eigenmode is the one that approaches a zero-dissipation in the zero-frequency limit. As expected, the physical eigenmode approaches the non-modal dissipation curve in the low-wavenumber

Fig. 1. Comparison between the non-modal dissipation of the p -multigrid operator (red), eigenmodes of the p -multigrid operator (dashed lines) and non-modal dissipation of the spatial FR operator (black line) at $P = 1, 2$. (For interpretation of the colours in the figure(s), the reader is referred to the web version of this article.)

Fig. 2. Non-modal dissipation curves of the p -multigrid operator (red) and spatial FR operator (black line) at orders $P = 3, \dots, 6$.

region. Following reasoning made in [38] and [40], the contrary happens in the high-wavenumber region, where all eigenmodes contribute in similar proportions. This is especially clear at $P = 1$, where the non-modal dissipation curve approaches that of the spurious eigenmode at high-frequencies. We note that the use of terms “physical” or “spurious” are probably not adequate in this context, as we are using a multigrid approach that does not try to accurately follow a physically meaningful transient behaviour. Rather, what we call the “physical eigenmode” in this context is the one responsible for the coarsest-level smoothing. Its range of influence in the frequency spectrum is therefore reduced at increasing polynomial orders, as it can be seen at $P = 2$.

5.1.2. Effect of the polynomial order

V-cycle p -multigrid is considered with only one smoothing step at each level. Figs. 1 and 2 compare, for polynomial orders $P = 1, \dots, 6$, the non-modal dissipation curve of p -multigrid and the corresponding spatial operator at the fine level. The mesh is uniform in all cases, $h = 1$. It is clearly seen how dissipation is increased in the low wavenumber range for all

Fig. 3. Scaled dissipation curves of V-cycle p -multigrid operators at $P = 3, \dots, 6$ with different sweep patterns.

orders, the difference becoming greater for higher polynomial orders. This suggests that the p -multigrid effectiveness would increase with the polynomial order.

5.1.3. Effect of the sweep pattern

Coarse-level sweeps are computationally inexpensive with respect to fine-level sweeps, therefore multigrid implementations usually perform more smoothing steps at coarser levels to increase low-wavenumber dissipation. We denote the sweep pattern (SP) as the number of smoothing steps used for each multigrid level. Let us consider three possible choices:

- $m_p \equiv 1$, constant (“all-ones”) SP. One pre-smoothing step and one post-smoothing step are performed at all levels. This is the choice made in the previous Fig. 2.
- $m_p = (P + 1) - p$, linear SP. $P + 1$ smoothing steps are performed at the coarsest level ($p = 0$).
- $m_p = 2^{P-p}$, geometric SP. 2^P sweeps are performed at $p = 0$.

Fig. 3 compares the dissipation curves at the same polynomial orders $P = 3, \dots, 6$ and the three sweep patterns considered. $P = 1$ and $P = 2$ are not shown since the difference between the sweep patterns is very small, which translates into the three curves being very close. The difference between linear SP and geometric SP grows with the polynomial order, presumably as the number of sweeps at low polynomial order $p \leq 1$ begins to increase. In fact, for $P \geq 4$ the difference in the dissipation becomes significant, suggesting that coarse-level sweeps are an effective way of accelerating convergence.

On the other hand, previous observations lead to ask whether $p = 0$ sweeps are actually effective. To that end, we compare, at $P = 2$ and $P = 3$, the effect on increasing the number of sweeps at $p = 0$ while leaving the rest of the sweep pattern unchanged. $P = 2$ and $P = 3$ are chosen because the number of multigrid levels is sufficiently low for $p = 0$ to still be relevant on its own, but not as relevant as in $p = 1$ where it is the only coarse level. Results can be seen in Fig. 4, confirming that indeed increasing the number of sweeps at $p = 0$ is not determinant to the dissipation rate. At $P = 3$ there is an unexpected increase in the high-wavenumber dissipation near $\phi = 3\pi/4$, which may be due to aliasing errors

Fig. 4. Dissipation curves of V-cycle p -multigrid operators at $P = 2$ and $P = 3$ with increasing number of $p = 0$ sweeps.

Fig. 5. Dissipation curves of V-cycle and W-cycle p -multigrid operators at $P = 2$ and $P = 3$. “ws” stands for the number of w-sweeps.

introduced by the restriction-prolongation operators. The limited efficiency of level $p = 0$ has also been reported in the literature [95] in the context of a discontinuous Galerkin discretization.

5.1.4. V-cycle and W-cycles

Fig. 5 shows the non-modal dissipation by means of V-cycles and W-cycles for $P = 2$ and $P = 3$, always using a geometric sweep pattern. In the W-cycle there is an extra parameter, the number of w-sweeps, that corresponds to the number of extra loops between $p = 1$ and $p = 0$ with respect to a V-cycle. For instance, at $P = 2$ with a geometric sweep pattern:

- The sequence of levels in a V-cycle is: $2 \rightarrow 1 \rightarrow 0 \rightarrow 1 \rightarrow 2$.
- The sequence in a W-cycle with 1 w-sweep is: $2 \rightarrow 1 \rightarrow 0 \rightarrow (1 \rightarrow 0) \rightarrow 1 \rightarrow 2$.
- The sequence in a W-cycle with 2 w-sweeps is: $2 \rightarrow 1 \rightarrow 0 \rightarrow (1 \rightarrow 0 \rightarrow 1 \rightarrow 0) \rightarrow 1 \rightarrow 2$.

At $P = 2$, the difference between V-cycles and W-cycles is relevant. For the same amount of fine-level smoothing, the additional coarse-level sweeps in the W-cycle bring in significantly more dissipation in the low- and mid-wavenumber range. The gains in dissipation are smaller at $P = 3$, and the trend remains for higher polynomial orders up to $P = 6$. It should be noted that, as the number of multigrid levels increases, it is only expected that the relative importance of $p = 1$ and $p = 0$ decreases, and therefore the advantage of using a two-level loop in the W-cycle is limited. Similar to increasing the number of coarse-level smoothing steps as in Fig. 4, the behaviour near the high-wavenumber limit remains largely unchanged.

Fig. 6. Dissipation curves of *hp*-multigrid operators with an increasing number of meshes. All operators use a geometric sweep pattern.

Fig. 7. Close-up of the low-wavenumber dissipation of *hp*-multigrid operators with an increasing number of meshes. All operators use a geometric sweep pattern.

5.1.5. *p*-multigrid and *hp*-multigrid

Next, combined *hp*-multigrid is considered by adding coarse meshes under the $p = 0$ level. Hence, an *hp*-multigrid with two meshes has one additional mesh with respect to *p*-multigrid. The *h*-multigrid levels are also solved at polynomial order 0. For the sake of simplicity, we only consider a geometric sweep pattern, as it has already shown to have the highest dissipation rate. In spite of the limited efficiency of increasing the $p = 0$ sweeps, as shown in section 5.1.3, the addition of coarser levels is still interesting to consider because of two reasons, namely (i) we seek an *h*-independent convergence rate as in conventional *h*-multigrid, which cannot be emulated using only *p*-multigrid if the mesh becomes more refined in *h*, and (ii) level $p = 0$ is still influential at low polynomial orders $P = 1, 2$, and improving coarse-level solutions by *h*-multigrid may result in convergence improvement at those orders. Fig. 6 plots the dissipation curves of the combined *hp*-multigrid

Fig. 8. Non-modal dissipation of V-cycle p -multigrid with geometric sweep pattern at increasing Péclet numbers.

operators compared to the p -multigrid. It can be seen that, with the addition of only one mesh, the numerical behaviour is not substantially different for higher polynomial orders ($P \geq 3$). One may draw two observations:

- Most of the frequency spectrum does not seem affected by the use of coarser meshes, which implies that the p -multigrid dominates the dissipation behaviour over the h -multigrid. Raising the number of h -levels (or coarser meshes) barely seems to increase the dissipation rate. Note that, by using a geometric sweep pattern and especially at high polynomial orders, the number of sweeps at the coarsest mesh becomes very high. The computational cost of doing such a number of smoothing steps should be considered against the marginal increase in the dissipation rate, especially for $P = 4$, where even the sole addition of more meshes is barely effective.
- However, in the limit $\phi \rightarrow 0$, there are significant differences in the dissipation rate, especially at low and moderate polynomial orders. Take for instance $\phi = \pi/16$, which at $P = 3$ represents an error wave of wavelength $\lambda = 8$. This means that a full length spans 8 cells, which seems reasonable for a low-frequency error in an actual simulation. Without h -multigrid, the damping factor of the V-cycle is $\varpi_p^*(\pi/16) = -3.3$; the same V-cycle with an additional mesh (hp -multigrid) has a damping $\varpi_{hp2}^*(\pi/16) = -6.6$, and with two more meshes it decreases down to $\varpi_{hp4}^*(\pi/16) = -12.6$ (see Fig. 7). This ratio is approximately maintained at $P > 3$, being even higher at $P \leq 2$, which is expected to translate into an improved convergence rate when the solution has a strong content in low-frequency errors. Therefore, in spite of the curves being visually similar, the use of hp -multigrid would still be advantageous.

5.2. 1D convection-diffusion

The previous analyses have been carried out in the context of pure diffusion, where the suitability of the multigrid as a convergence accelerator is out of question. Loosely speaking, there is always a steady-state solution of the LCDE as long as the diffusion coefficient is positive; however, increasing the convection velocity will result in wave-like transient behaviour. In this section we show how the presence of convection affects the dissipation of multigrid schemes. To that end we introduce the cell Péclet number:

Fig. 9. Transient dissipative behaviour of the V-cycle p -multigrid operator at $P = 4$, $Pe = \infty$, and several time-step magnitudes.

Fig. 10. Dissipation of multigrid operators for 1D linear convection-diffusion at $Pe = 10$. W-cycles consist of two w-sweeps and hp -multigrid uses 2 additional meshes (3 in total).

$$Pe = \frac{|a|h^*}{\nu} = \frac{|a|h}{(P+1)\nu}. \tag{28}$$

Following what has been shown in the literature, high degree of convection can degrade the performance of the multigrid [91], and the same applies to high aspect-ratio meshes [93]. Therefore, we look for those multigrid configurations that damp the expected reduction in the dissipation rate.

The dissipation of V-cycle p -multigrid with geometric sweep pattern for $P = 1, \dots, 4$ is shown in Fig. 8 for different values of the Péclet number. The low- and mid-wavenumber dissipation is most affected by the presence of convection, seeing a significant decrease in the damping factor, especially at high polynomial orders. Overall, the dissipation decreases as the Péclet number increases, and is greatly reduced at already moderate convection ($Pe = 10$). The curve $Pe = \infty$ has also been plotted for both the multigrid and the spatial FR operator, even though a pure-convection problem has no steady solution, to illustrate the similarity between $Pe = 10$ and pure-convection. Of particular interest is the anti-dissipative behaviour of the multigrid in convection-dominated flows at $P \geq 3$. While, as explained in section 4.3, positive damping factors are not necessarily related to a long-term unstable scheme, they imply a transient growth in the magnitude of the error and are therefore detrimental to the multigrid efficiency.

More insights are given below by studying the behaviour of the V-cycle p -multigrid at $P = 4$ in pure convection, i.e. the green curve in Fig. 8(d). Let us select a normalised frequency $\phi = \pi/2$ for the initial solution, which according to the non-modal analysis corresponds to a diffusion coefficient of about $\varpi_{\pi/2}^*(\tau^* = 0) = 4.46 > 0$. We have intentionally emphasized $\tau^* = 0$, as we would now like to generalize the damping factor as $\varpi_{\pi/2}^*(\tau^*)$, where the derivative from definition (24) is now evaluated at an arbitrary τ^* , instead of $\tau^* = 0$. Clearly, the solution will be damped in those time intervals in which $\varpi_{\pi/2}^*(\tau^*)$ is negative, and will grow in those intervals in which $\varpi_{\pi/2}^*(\tau^*)$ is positive. For an asymptotically stable behaviour, $\varpi_{\pi/2}^*(\tau^* \rightarrow \infty) < 0$ is imperative.

Fig. 11. Dissipation surfaces at $P = 2$ for a pure diffusion case with uniform mesh, $h_x = h_y$.

In Fig. 9(a), we have plotted the curves $\varpi_{\pi/2}^*(\tau^*)$ at different values of Δt for the aforementioned multigrid operator. These curves are obtained marching in time using explicit Forward Euler as a smoother, where in the limit $\Delta t \rightarrow 0$ we obtain a curve devoid of time-integration errors and temporal dissipation. In the right Fig. 9(b), the evolution of the magnitude of the solution is plotted. Three main observations can be drawn from these two graphs:

- Despite the initially positive damping factor, the τ^* -evolution for $\Delta t \rightarrow 0$ reveals a stable scheme in which the solution is damped in time. The solution grows initially, as shown in the right plot, and the value of this initial slope is the one recovered by the non-modal dissipation curve of Fig. 8. However, this growth is only transient and, at all considered values of Δt , the asymptotic value of the non-modal dissipation is below zero, which fulfills the stability condition. This final value is reached at around $\tau^* = 1$.
- Furthermore, the asymptotic behaviour of the non-modal dissipation coefficient reconciles with the von Neumann analysis in that the long-term convergence rate is dictated by the “least-stable” eigenvalue of the system. In fact, it is easily confirmed that $\varpi_{\pi/2}(\tau^* = 1)$ approaches $\max\{\mathcal{R}e\left(\frac{\ln \lambda_k}{\Delta t}\right)\}$, where $\{\lambda_k\}$ are the eigenvalues of the multigrid operator. This value is -0.246 in the limit $\Delta t \rightarrow 0$.
- Although we are not interested in the fully-discrete analysis since this works focuses only on spatial dissipation, it is interesting to note how the non-modal coefficient changes at increasing time-steps, especially the initial value, even if the long-term behaviour remains largely unchanged. In practice, one seeks to use the largest time-step possible, and in such cases the dissipation introduced by the temporal discretization can prevent the initial anti-dissipation from happening. Overall, these results reveal the importance of the long-term vs. short-term behaviour as well as the influence of the smoother’s dissipation, and the authors acknowledge they should be further explored to draw the non-modal analysis closer to practical applications.

From previous results it had been shown that W-cycles or hp -multigrid increases the dissipation, so applying them in mixed convection-diffusion may help in counteracting the *flattening* of the curves at higher Péclet numbers. Fig. 10 compares several multigrid strategies at $P = 2$ and $P = 3$, from where it is seen that (i) W-cycles increase the overall dissipation, especially in the mid- and high-wavenumber region although a decrease in dissipation near $\phi = \pi/2$ is seen at $P = 3$, (ii) hp -multigrid increases the low-wavenumber dissipation and (iii) the combined use of W-cycles and hp -multigrid retains both advantages, yielding overall the most efficient scheme for mixed convection-diffusion. This trend maintains for higher polynomial orders. In the next section, we will cover how the results shown so far extend to 2D and in the presence of high aspect-ratio cells.

5.3. 2D convection-diffusion

In 2D, two independent wavenumbers ϕ_x and ϕ_y define the initial wave. Therefore, we show dissipation surfaces rather than dissipation curves. The initial condition is a plane wave forming an angle with the x -axis given by $\theta = \tan^{-1}(\kappa_y/\kappa_x)$. This plane wave is parallel to the x -axis when $\kappa_y = 0$ and parallel to the y -axis when $\kappa_x = 0$.

5.3.1. 2D diffusion on square cells

In Fig. 11 we can see the dissipation surfaces at $P = 2$ of a 2D diffusion problem. With respect to the V-cycle, the W-cycle increases the dissipation in the whole frequency spectrum, and the hp -multigrid has a sharper decrease in the damping factor at very low frequencies: all of this is consistent with what has been reported in 1D, and the same trend applies to polynomial orders $P = 1, \dots, 6$ alike. We find that the behaviour of multigrid operators extend naturally from 1D to 2D square meshes in the case of pure diffusion; therefore we avoid unnecessary repetitions and focus on high aspect-ratio cells and mixed convection-diffusion instead.

Fig. 12. Scaled non-modal dissipation $\varpi^* r_h^{-2}$ of a V-cycle p -multigrid with increasing aspect-ratios at $P = 2$, for a pure diffusion problem.

Fig. 13. Scaled non-modal dissipation $\varpi^* r_h^{-1}$ of linear convection-diffusion at $Pe = 10^3$ with V-cycle p -multigrid at increasing aspect-ratios.

5.3.2. 2D diffusion on high aspect-ratio cells

We define the aspect ratio as the quotient of characteristic lengths in the cell, $r_h = h_x/h_y$. A high aspect-ratio cell is thin in the y -direction, and comparatively long in the x -direction. The cell length is kept constant, $h_x = 1$. When comparing the non-modal dissipation of high aspect-ratio cells, one should bear in mind the difference in the maximum time-step size for each case. Knowing that the viscous time-step restriction scales with h^2 , where h is a characteristic length, we choose to scale the damping factor of the non-modal dissipation by a factor of r_h^{-2} . Fig. 12 shows the scaled non-modal dissipation $\varpi^* r_h^{-2}$ of a V-cycle p -multigrid with increasing aspect-ratios. Note that the non-modal dissipation curve with $r_h = 1$ coincides with that of Fig. 11. As the aspect ratio increases, there are some significant changes in the shape of the dissipation surface. The region of high damping, located in the mid-wavenumber range for $r_h = 1$, is displaced to the low-wavenumber region $\phi_x \rightarrow 0$ for higher values of r_h . Damping is also greatly reduced in the presence of low-frequency errors in the y -direction. Moreover, the dissipation surfaces at $r_h = 10$ and $r_h = 1000$ are very similar and show the importance of performing a 2D numerical analysis as opposed to extrapolating results from a 1D analysis, which is naturally simpler. On the other hand, the high-wavenumber dissipation remains approximately the same in all cases.

5.3.3. High Péclet convection on high aspect-ratio cells

For simplicity we only consider convection speeds $a_x = 1$ and $a_y = 0$, so convection happens along the x -axis, and a Péclet number of $Pe = 10^3$ which implies $\nu = 0.001$. For convection-dominated flows, one may approximate that the maximum allowable time-step scales with h^{-1} and therefore the scaled dissipation is taken as $\varpi^* r_h^{-1}$. At $P = 2$ and using a V-cycle p -multigrid, Fig. 13 shows the dissipation surfaces at increasing aspect-ratios. In a square cell, the surface is regular and monotonic, and it can be easily connected to the 1D analogous curve shown in Fig. 8. The behaviour changes drastically as we move to an aspect-ratio $r_h = 10$, seeing an overall decrease in dissipation especially for the low-frequency, y -component of the errors which remains largely undamped. On the other hand, as the aspect ratio increases further, the damping factors of the high-frequency, y -component of the errors decrease comparatively while the overall shape of the surface becomes similar to that of Fig. 12. This implies that very high aspect-ratios dominate the multigrid behaviour over the relative importance of convection or diffusion.

To mitigate the dissipation reduction in high aspect-ratio, one may propose to use W-cycles and hp -multigrid. It was shown in Fig. 10 that this strategy has a certain efficiency in mixed convection-diffusion, and we obtain similar results when applied to high aspect-ratios, see Fig. 14. The W-cycle effectively doubles the maximum dissipation and the use of hp -multigrid shows higher damping near the low-wavenumber region in ϕ_y . As in the case of Fig. 10, the hp -multigrid with W-cycles retains the advantages of both W-cycles and hp -multigrid. The trends observed in this section maintain at higher polynomial orders, as it can be seen in Fig. 15.

Fig. 14. Scaled non-modal dissipation $\varpi^* r_h^{-1}$ of linear convection-diffusion at $Pe = 10^3$, $r_h = 10^3$ and $P = 2$ with different multigrid configurations.

Fig. 15. Scaled non-modal dissipation $\varpi^* r_h^{-1}$ of linear convection-diffusion at $Pe = 10^3$ and $r_h = 10^3$ with V-cycle p -multigrid at increasing polynomial orders.

6. Verification with a method of manufactured solutions

We now solve two simple, linear convection-diffusion problems in 1D using multigrid methods and compare the convergence rate against the results of the non-modal analysis. The test cases are steady manufactured solutions proposed in [98] to assess the numerical properties of Flux Reconstruction. In order to measure the experimental convergence, in each one of the simulations we will compute the convergence factor ρ :

$$\rho = \frac{d}{dt} \ln ||r|| \simeq \frac{1}{N_I \Delta t} \ln \left(\frac{||r_{N_I}||}{||r_0||} \right), \tag{29}$$

where N_I is the number of iterations with time-step Δt needed to achieve a certain residual norm $||r_{N_I}||$. While other definitions for the convergence factor are more common in the literature (see for instance [97]), we choose expression (29) so that ρ has a similar definition to the non-modal dissipation. Contrary to the literature where the convergence factor takes values between 0 and 1, here the convergence factor is negative, and more negative values imply a faster convergence. Additionally, by dividing by $N_I \Delta t$ instead of just N_I the convergence factor is made independent of the time-step, so that it better illustrates the convergence speed of the *multigrid configuration* irrespective of the time-step size. One can think of ρ as an *experimental* damping factor, while ϖ^* would be a *theoretical* damping factor. In the absence of external forces, the value of ρ is expected to approach $\varpi = \varpi^*/T$ for a given error frequency k , where the time scaling factor T from equation (25) must be introduced to express the non-modal dissipation in terms of dimensional time t - note the lack of an asterisk in ϖ . The damping factor will also depend on the shape of a source term, such as the ones used in the manufactured solution case, but doing so results into a loss of generality of the analysis. Therefore and without loss of generality, we prefer to leave the source term out of the estimation of the damping factor and see whether the dissipation curves presented throughout this study still provide good predictions of the convergence rate.

Time-marching (or smoothing operations) is done using the Optimal Runge-Kutta (ORK) schemes recently developed by Vermeire et al. [102], whose coefficients have been optimized for FR-DG discretizations of linear advection in order to maximize the allowable time-step while dropping time-accuracy. As this study focuses on multigrid marching to a steady-state solution, neither is time-accuracy of interest here.

6.1. 1D periodic wave

The computational domain comprises the interval $x \in [-\pi, \pi]$ with periodic boundary conditions. The linear convection-diffusion in 1D is to be solved with a constant source term $s(x)$ and the corresponding steady-state analytical solution $u_e(x)$ being as follows [98]:

$$s(x) = -ak \left(\frac{a}{v} \cos(kx) + k \sin(kx) \right), \quad (30)$$

$$u_e(x) = -\frac{a}{v} \sin(kx), \quad (31)$$

where we have introduced $k = 1, 2, 4, 8, \dots$ as an additional free parameter. The steady solution is a sinusoidal function of amplitude a/v . In this study, we will use $u_0(x) \equiv 0$ as an initial condition, and therefore it can be seen that the initial error is a wave of the same frequency as the steady solution itself. This allows to use the test case to assess the convergence rate of the multigrid for a single wavenumber, which can be related to a single value of the non-modal dissipation $\varpi(\phi)$. We will focus on mixed convection-diffusion with $a = 1$ and $v = 1$, and polynomial orders $P = 1, \dots, 6$. The case setup is as follows. For a given polynomial order P , the domain is divided in a number of cells N_C , which for the zero-initial condition yields the following error wavenumber ϕ :

$$\phi = \frac{2\pi k}{(P+1)N_C}. \quad (32)$$

We will focus on the behaviour in the low-frequency spectrum by using fine meshes and alternating between $k = 1$ and $k = 2$. The normalized wavenumber ϕ is used to compute the theoretical damping factor $\varpi(\phi)$ for the multigrid configuration being tested. The system is solved by marching to steady state until the cell-average L^2 norm of the residuals drops below 10^{-6} with respect to the initial residual, and then the convergence factor ρ is computed. The time-step size is chosen between $0.5 \times \Delta t_{\max}$ and $0.6 \times \Delta t_{\max}$, with Δt_{\max} the stability limit of the fine-level smoother.

The results are shown in Table 1. A total of 44 simulations have tested, for polynomial orders 1 to 6, the most common multigrid configurations: p -multigrid with V-cycles, p -multigrid with W-cycles, hp -multigrid with V-cycles and hp -multigrid with W-cycles. The geometric sweep pattern is used in all configurations. Two w-sweeps are used in the W-cycles, and one additional mesh is used in hp -multigrid. The main outputs of Table 1 are the values of the experimental convergence rate ρ and the theoretical factor ϖ . Very good agreement is shown in most cases. With the exception of some clearly discrepant values (e.g. $P = 4$, $k = 2$ with W-cycle p -multigrid), the relative error between experimental and theoretical rates of convergence is below 10%, which seems satisfactory for predictive purposes. Of particular notice is that the non-modal damping factor, being representative of short-term dynamics, can predict long-term behaviour with surprising accuracy in cases in which a large number of iterations is needed to converge (see V-cycle p -multigrid at $k = 1$ for $P = 1, 2, 3$). However, one would accordingly expect the non-modal analysis to better estimate the higher convergence rates. This is clearly not the case – see for instance $P = 5$, $k = 2$ for W-cycle hp -multigrid –, probably due to the following:

- The non-modal dissipation is obtained in the time-continuous limit $\Delta t \rightarrow 0$. Hence, we are approximating the dissipation behaviour of a multigrid operator in the same way that we would approximate the properties of a discrete scheme – in space and time – by the properties of the spatial discretization operator. The dispersion and dissipation curves are known to be more sensitive to time-discretization errors in the high-wavenumber range – see [30]. This would explain why simulations at higher error wavenumbers yield higher discrepancies between ρ and ϖ .
- In the case of a very fast convergence (see W-cycle hp -multigrid at $P = 5, 6$), the approximation used for computing the convergence factor, equation (29), may also yield higher errors. It can be shown that reducing the time-step makes ρ approach ϖ , which is theoretically consistent.

The convergence rate predictions from eigenanalysis (von Neumann analysis) are listed in the rightmost column of Table 1, under the label “VNA”. They correspond to the asymptotic convergence rates, determined by the eigenspectrum of each operator as briefly discussed in section 5.2. It is known that at lower frequencies the dynamic behaviour of the system is dominated by the primary eigenmode, and therefore the predictions from von Neumann and non-modal analysis are consistently similar for $k = 1$. In the case $k = 2$, all eigenmodes gain comparative importance and the von Neumann analysis should depart from the short-term dissipation, which is more clearly visible for hp -multigrid. In general, for hp -multigrid the non-modal dissipation rate is closer to the experimental one, with some exceptions previously addressed. Finally, it is worth noting the improvement in the convergence rate as the polynomial order increases. All simulations using p -multigrid have a comparable number of degrees of freedom (around 30), and as the polynomial order increases, the number of iterations decreases steadily even if the time-step is also lower. This is probably due to the increasing number of multigrid p -levels for higher values of P . For the V-cycle hp -multigrid at $P > 2$ and even more for the highly efficient W-cycle hp -multigrid, the number of iterations N_I required to converge is maintained approximately constant as the number of degrees of freedom increases with P . In all those cases the cell width is the same, $h = 0.7854$, and thus the results can be considered as a rough indication on the quasi- h -independence on the convergence of hp -multigrid.

Table 1

Convergence data for the 1D periodic problem with $a = 1$, $\nu = 1$. All multigrid operators use geometric sweep pattern; W-cycles use 2 w-sweeps and hp-multigrid use one additional mesh. The same time-step is used across all levels, and required relative residual drop is 10^{-6} . P is the polynomial order, k the wavenumber, ϕ the corresponding non-dimensional wavenumber, h is the cell width, N_C number of mesh cells, N_I the number of iterations to convergence. ρ is the experimental damping factor, $\varpi(\phi)$ the predicted non-modal damping factor, and "VNA" shows the von Neumann predicted damping factors.

P	k	h	N_C	Multigrid	N_I	Δt	ϕ	ρ	$\varpi(\phi)$	VNA
1	1	0.3927	16	V-cycle p -multigrid	360	$9.6 \cdot 10^{-3}$	0.1963	-4.00	-3.99	-4.00
1	2	0.3927	16	V-cycle p -multigrid	89	$9.6 \cdot 10^{-3}$	0.3927	-16.17	-15.81	-15.97
1	1	0.3927	16	V-cycle hp -multigrid	127	$9.6 \cdot 10^{-3}$	0.1963	-11.33	-9.72	-5.94
1	2	0.3927	16	V-cycle hp -multigrid	35	$9.6 \cdot 10^{-3}$	0.3927	-41.12	-35.95	-22.93
2	1	0.5712	11	V-cycle p -multigrid	261	$5.4 \cdot 10^{-3}$	0.1904	-9.80	-9.88	-9.82
2	2	0.5712	11	V-cycle p -multigrid	68	$5.4 \cdot 10^{-3}$	0.3808	-37.62	-38.40	-37.09
2	1	0.5712	11	W-cycle p -multigrid	120	$5.4 \cdot 10^{-3}$	0.1904	-21.32	-21.64	-21.29
2	2	0.5712	11	W-cycle p -multigrid	31	$5.4 \cdot 10^{-3}$	0.3808	-82.53	-83.15	-76.43
2	1	0.6283	10	V-cycle hp -multigrid	108	$5.5 \cdot 10^{-3}$	0.2094	-23.26	-20.68	-13.41
2	2	0.6283	10	V-cycle hp -multigrid	34	$5.5 \cdot 10^{-3}$	0.4189	-73.88	-70.57	-47.15
2	1	0.6283	10	W-cycle hp -multigrid	73	$5.5 \cdot 10^{-3}$	0.2094	-34.41	-32.39	-24.66
2	2	0.6283	10	W-cycle hp -multigrid	21	$5.5 \cdot 10^{-3}$	0.4189	-119.61	-114.73	-83.24
3	1	0.7854	8	V-cycle p -multigrid	155	$4.2 \cdot 10^{-3}$	0.1963	-21.22	-21.59	-21.36
3	2	0.7854	8	V-cycle p -multigrid	42	$4.2 \cdot 10^{-3}$	0.3927	-78.32	-81.65	-78.07
3	1	0.7854	8	W-cycle p -multigrid	76	$4.2 \cdot 10^{-3}$	0.1963	-43.28	-44.79	-43.49
3	2	0.7854	8	W-cycle p -multigrid	21	$4.2 \cdot 10^{-3}$	0.3927	-156.64	-165.28	-146.14
3	1	0.7854	8	V-cycle hp -multigrid	86	$3.5 \cdot 10^{-3}$	0.1963	-45.90	-42.17	-28.33
3	2	0.7854	8	V-cycle hp -multigrid	30	$3.5 \cdot 10^{-3}$	0.3927	-131.58	-133.60	-96.42
3	1	0.7854	8	W-cycle hp -multigrid	59	$3.5 \cdot 10^{-3}$	0.1963	-66.90	-65.36	-50.17
3	2	0.7854	8	W-cycle hp -multigrid	17	$3.5 \cdot 10^{-3}$	0.3927	-232.19	-217.24	-161.43
4	1	1.0472	6	V-cycle p -multigrid	89	$3.6 \cdot 10^{-3}$	0.2094	-43.12	-44.56	-43.82
4	2	1.0472	6	V-cycle p -multigrid	27	$3.6 \cdot 10^{-3}$	0.4189	-142.13	-162.08	-152.06
4	1	1.0472	6	W-cycle p -multigrid	46	$3.6 \cdot 10^{-3}$	0.2094	-83.43	-89.72	-85.53
4	2	1.0472	6	W-cycle p -multigrid	20	$3.6 \cdot 10^{-3}$	0.4189	-191.88	-311.87	-173.78
4	1	0.7854	8	V-cycle hp -multigrid	98	$1.5 \cdot 10^{-3}$	0.1571	-93.98	-86.32	-58.78
4	2	0.7854	8	V-cycle hp -multigrid	34	$1.5 \cdot 10^{-3}$	0.3142	-270.89	-275.04	-201.99
4	1	0.7854	8	W-cycle hp -multigrid	67	$1.5 \cdot 10^{-3}$	0.1571	-137.47	-132.70	-102.54
4	2	0.7854	8	W-cycle hp -multigrid	21	$1.5 \cdot 10^{-3}$	0.3142	-438.59	-442.22	-335.81
5	1	1.2566	5	V-cycle p -multigrid	67	$2.4 \cdot 10^{-3}$	0.2094	-85.92	-89.90	-87.87
5	2	1.2566	5	V-cycle p -multigrid	22	$2.4 \cdot 10^{-3}$	0.4189	-261.66	-315.31	-285.58
5	1	1.2566	5	W-cycle p -multigrid	35	$2.4 \cdot 10^{-3}$	0.2094	-164.47	-177.80	-166.54
5	2	1.2566	5	W-cycle p -multigrid	16	$2.4 \cdot 10^{-3}$	0.4189	-359.78	-584.11	-367.40
5	1	0.7854	8	V-cycle hp -multigrid	74	$1.0 \cdot 10^{-3}$	0.1309	-186.70	-174.64	-119.65
5	2	0.7854	8	V-cycle hp -multigrid	26	$1.0 \cdot 10^{-3}$	0.2618	-531.37	-558.23	-413.50
5	1	0.7854	8	W-cycle hp -multigrid	51	$1.0 \cdot 10^{-3}$	0.1309	-270.89	-267.40	-207.27
5	2	0.7854	8	W-cycle hp -multigrid	19	$1.0 \cdot 10^{-3}$	0.2618	-727.13	-892.72	-642.34
6	1	1.2566	5	V-cycle p -multigrid	45	$1.8 \cdot 10^{-3}$	0.1795	-170.56	-181.80	-177.81
6	2	1.2566	5	V-cycle p -multigrid	33	$1.8 \cdot 10^{-3}$	0.3590	-232.58	-638.53	-166.72
6	1	1.2566	5	W-cycle p -multigrid	25	$1.8 \cdot 10^{-3}$	0.1795	-307.01	-357.60	-335.32
6	2	1.2566	5	W-cycle p -multigrid	35	$1.8 \cdot 10^{-3}$	0.3590	-219.29	-1175.98	-166.72
6	1	0.7854	8	V-cycle hp -multigrid	73	$5.0 \cdot 10^{-4}$	0.1122	-378.51	-351.27	-241.41
6	2	0.7854	8	V-cycle hp -multigrid	26	$5.0 \cdot 10^{-4}$	0.2244	-1062.73	-1124.48	-836.51
6	1	0.7854	8	W-cycle hp -multigrid	51	$5.0 \cdot 10^{-4}$	0.1122	-541.78	-536.79	-416.72
6	2	0.7854	8	W-cycle hp -multigrid	25	$5.0 \cdot 10^{-4}$	0.2244	-1105.24	-1793.47	-917.77

6.2. 1D boundary-layer

The next test-case is a wall-bounded manufactured solution which mimics a boundary-layer profile. The simulation domain is the interval $0 \leq x \leq 1$ with Dirichlet boundary conditions $u(0) = 0$ and $u(1) = 1$. Inside the domain, the analytical source term and the exact solution are [98]:

$$s(x) = \frac{\pi \nu}{a} [a \cos(\pi x) + \pi \nu \sin(\pi x)], \tag{33}$$

$$u_e(x) = \frac{\exp(-a/\nu) - \exp((x-1)a/\nu)}{\exp(-a/\nu) - 1} + \frac{\nu}{a} \sin(\pi x). \tag{34}$$

As in [98], we plot the analytical solution for several values of a/ν in Fig. 16. While previously the error wavenumber was known and unique, that information is not available now and therefore we resort to the frequency-averaged dissipation, $\langle \varpi \rangle$ as a simplified representation of the theoretical predictions. Likewise, due to the presence of errors of different

Fig. 16. Analytical solution of the manufactured 1D boundary-layer problem from [98] for several values of the ratio a/v .

Table 2

Convergence data for the 1D boundary-layer problem with V-cycle p -multigrid operators using geometric sweep pattern. The computational domain is divided in $N_C = 20$ elements ($h = 0.05$). DOFs stands for the total number of degrees of freedom. $N_{l,-1}$ is the number of iterations required for the residuals to drop one order of magnitude, and $N_{l,-10}$ the required iterations for a residual drop of ten orders of magnitude.

P	a/v	DOFs	$N_{l,-1}$	$N_{l,-10}$	Δt	$\hat{\rho}_{-1}$	$\hat{\rho}_{-10}$	$(P + 1)\langle\varpi^*\rangle$
1	1	40	56	1764	$1.17 \cdot 10^{-3}$	-1370.59	-43.51	-7293.79
1	10	40	12	819	$1.94 \cdot 10^{-3}$	-1023.37	-14.99	-959.17
1	100	40	6	134	$6.78 \cdot 10^{-3}$	-913.72	-40.91	-325.72
2	1	60	49	3441	$6.0 \cdot 10^{-5}$	-7831.92	-111.53	-35908.20
2	10	60	15	1444	$4.2 \cdot 10^{-4}$	-3654.90	-37.97	-3895.59
2	100	60	6	116	$1.6 \cdot 10^{-3}$	-2368.91	-122.53	-694.56
3	1	80	6	4410	$2.0 \cdot 10^{-5}$	-191882.09	-261.06	-116279.89
3	10	80	6	4245	$6.0 \cdot 10^{-5}$	-63960.70	-90.40	-11918.39
3	100	80	4	295	$2.8 \cdot 10^{-4}$	-20558.80	-278.76	-1482.83
4	1	100	17	5276	$7.5 \cdot 10^{-6}$	-180594.91	-581.90	-296018.71
4	10	100	10	7762	$1.5 \cdot 10^{-5}$	-153505.67	-197.77	-29785.29
4	100	100	3	670	$6.0 \cdot 10^{-5}$	-127921.39	-572.78	-3151.96

frequencies, the residual drop plot may not be linear in logarithmic scale, so the convergence factor ρ is no longer constant but time-averaged ($\hat{\rho}$). As a result, we perform the comparison between non-modal analysis and actual convergence from a more qualitative point of view. The setup is as follows. The mesh is split into $N_C = 20$ elements with length $h = 0.05$. The polynomial order goes from 1 to 4, and for each one we try the V-cycle p -multigrid against increasing ratios of a/v . Multigrid iterations are applied until residuals drop below 10^{-1} , compute an early convergence factor $\hat{\rho}_{-1}$, and then continue until a residual drop of 10^{-10} and compute a second convergence factor $\hat{\rho}_{-10}$, both following the same equation (29).

The results with V-cycle p -multigrid at increasing values of a/v are shown in Table 2. Firstly, we focus on the results for the convergence factors. The short-term convergence factor $\hat{\rho}_{-1}$ decreases as a/v becomes higher for all polynomial orders, which is an expected result (see Fig. 8). Assuming that the frequency content of the errors is richer at the initial stages of the simulation, before high-frequency errors are damped, this factor $\hat{\rho}_{-1}$ is closer to what the average dissipation $(P + 1)\langle\varpi\rangle$ is representing in this case, although we emphasize that they are not mathematically related. $(P + 1)\langle\varpi\rangle$ would represent a short-term damping factor assuming an equal distribution for the error wavenumber, and would also not be constant throughout the simulation since, as high-frequency errors are damped out, only low-wavenumber errors are left for which the damping factor is much lower. Overall, the interest in computing $\langle\varpi\rangle$ for predictive purposes is debatable, but from an academic point of view, it is interesting to note that $\hat{\rho}_{-1}$ and $\langle\varpi\rangle$ follow the same trend – decreasing as the ratio a/v increases. This points to the possibility of finding more elaborated quantities instead of a rough average $\langle\varpi\rangle$ to better estimate the actual behaviour with mixed error frequencies, something that remains for future investigation.

The long-term convergence factor $\hat{\rho}_{-10}$ is orders of magnitude lower, and also more similar to the convergence factors computed for the 1D periodic wave case. For all polynomial orders we see that the convergence factor worsens significantly from $a/v = 1$ to $a/v = 10$, but improves again for $a/v = 100$, contradicting the expectations. In order to explain this, we argue that the manufactured solution at $a/v = 100$ has a sharp profile and that, departing from a zero-initial solution, the initial error intuitively has a heavy high-frequency component. Additionally, the analytical solution having the following term:

$$\frac{v}{a} \sin(\pi x), \tag{35}$$

we know that the initial error contains a low-frequency wave with non-dimensional wavenumber $\phi = \pi h/(P + 1)$, with $h = 0.05$, whose amplitude decreases at higher degrees of convection. This suggests that the improved convergence at higher convection is also case-dependent.

The long-term convergence factor $\hat{\rho}_{-10}$ also becomes more negative as the polynomial order increases, but without translating into faster convergence rates. Higher degrees of convection consistently require a smaller number of iterations, and higher polynomial orders increase the number of iterations. The explanation could lie in what has been argued in the previous paragraph, but also in the allowable time-step. Notice the sharp decrease in the time-step used from one polynomial order to the next (the time-step was chosen following the same criterion as for the 1D periodic wave). Also, higher ratios of a/ν can use higher time-steps, since the viscosity coefficient is decreasing and the convection velocity is kept constant, so the viscous time-step restriction fades away. All in all, the time-step stability limit obviously influences the required number of iterations, and this is not taken into account by the non-modal analysis. Therefore, the interpretation of $\overline{\omega}$ onto an expected convergence rate or computational cost should be made with caution. Altogether, after showing in the first test-case how the non-modal analysis can successfully estimate damping rates of single-frequency errors, this test-case illustrates some of its limitations as a tool for quantitative predictions.

7. Conclusions

In this paper, we have presented an application of the non-modal analysis (NMA) to study the numerical behaviour of multigrid schemes in Flux Reconstruction. The FR discretization of linear convection-diffusion has been briefly explained, and a compact matrix form has been obtained for a generic p - or hp -multigrid operator. This has allowed to assess the non-modal (short-term) dissipation of a number of multigrid configurations, in the frequency domain, assuming that a stronger dissipation is indicative of a faster convergence rate.

The analysis has first focused on 1D diffusion, where it has been shown that the non-modal dissipation is higher for a p -multigrid operator than for an FR spatial operator at order P , and that the increase in dissipation is more pronounced at higher polynomial orders. Also, increasing the number of coarse-level smoothing steps by means of the so-called geometric sweep pattern – performing 2^{P-p} sweeps at level p – effectively increases the multigrid damping factors. Similar effects are observed by using W -cycles instead of V -cycles, or by using hp -multigrid with an increasing number of coarse meshes – h -multigrid levels. In particular, the hp -multigrid appears to add significant damping for very low-wavenumber errors.

The non-modal analysis has been extended to mixed convection-diffusion, where it has been observed that higher Péclet numbers decrease the dissipation rates especially at higher polynomial orders. This can be partially counteracted by the use of W -cycles and hp -multigrid. The analysis results extend naturally to 2D cartesian meshes, where again convection-diffusion translated into reduced dissipation and a similar conclusion can be drawn for high aspect-ratio meshes.

The analysis has been compared against simulations results of manufactured solutions proposed in [98]. A steady 1D periodic-wave problem has been considered, the convergence factors predicted by the non-modal analysis showing very good agreement with the experimental ones. This test-case has demonstrated the increase in multigrid efficiency at higher polynomial orders, and same has been confirmed for the use of W -cycles and hp -multigrid to increase low-wavenumber damping. Next, we have assessed in a 1D boundary-layer problem the capability of non-modal analysis to predict convergence in cases where the frequency content of the errors is not known *a priori*. The short-term damping observed in simulations follow the same trend as an averaged damping factor $\langle \overline{\omega} \rangle$ obtained from non-modal dissipation curves. In this case, higher damping does not translate into an improvement in convergence, highlighting some of the current limitations of this analysis. As used in this paper, the NMA does not take into account time-step restrictions and therefore an increase in the damping factor might be neutralized by a smaller stability limit. Along these lines, an extension of the non-modal analysis for finite time-steps $\Delta t > 0$ is necessary to obtain convergence factors per iteration, which are more pertinent for convergence acceleration. Along these lines, the analysis of fully discrete operators with finite time-steps would allow to extend the NMA to Dual-Time-Stepping schemes in which the time derivative in physical time is added as a source term, and especially to assess the range of ratios of physical step size to pseudo step size in which the multigrid remains stable for any given combination of time discretizations. This would bring closer the non-modal analysis to practical settings in CFD, and will be considered for future work. A non-modal analysis of a fully-discrete operator would also improve the damping factor estimations against actual simulations, especially in the high-wavenumber range. Finally, based on the ability of the NMA to predict the convergence behaviour for single-frequency errors, an effort to more tightly relate the dissipation curves to convergence in more complex simulations remains for future work.

CRedit authorship contribution statement

Aurelio Hurtado-de-Mendoza: Conceptualization, Formal analysis, Investigation, Methodology, Software, Validation, Visualization, Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing. **Jiaqing Kou:** Formal analysis, Investigation, Software, Validation, Visualization. **Saumitra Joshi:** Formal analysis, Investigation, Validation. **Kunal Puri:** Conceptualization, Project administration, Supervision, Visualization. **Charles Hirsch:** Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Project administration, Supervision. **Esteban Ferrer:** Conceptualization, Funding acquisition, Project administration, Supervision, Visualization, Writing – review & editing.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

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Appendix A. Matrix formulation of the Correction Scheme multigrid operator

The interested reader will find in this section a detailed explanation on how the multigrid matrices of a p -multigrid operator are obtained for an arbitrary number of levels, assuming the use of explicit smoothers.

Let us use subscript $p = 0, \dots, P$ to denote each multigrid level, where P is the finest level and 0 the coarsest one. The Correction Scheme [50] is formulated by solving the full system at the fine level and the residual equation at the coarse levels:

$$\mathcal{A}_p \mathbf{u}_p = \mathbf{f}_p, \quad \begin{cases} \mathbf{f}_p = \mathbf{R}_{p+1}^p \mathbf{r}_{p+1} \\ \mathbf{r}_p = \mathbf{f}_p - \mathcal{A}_p \mathbf{u}_p \end{cases}, \quad p = 0, \dots, P-1. \quad (\text{A.1})$$

This equation introduces the basic ingredients of the multigrid:

- The spatial discretization operator at each level, \mathcal{A}_p . In our case, this is the Flux Reconstruction discretization of the divergence of the fluxes, and depends on the convection speed and diffusion coefficient, the FR scheme chosen, the mesh characteristics and the parameters of the Riemann solvers.
- The restriction and prolongation matrices, $\mathbf{R}_{p'}^p$, from level p to level p' . This matrices perform an L^2 -projection of the solution polynomial at order p into the corresponding target space of order p' .
- The residual at level p , \mathbf{r}_p , and the forcing terms at each level, \mathbf{f}_p , knowing that, in this work, at the fine level we don't consider any source term, $\mathbf{f}_P = \mathbf{0}$.

In order to perform a multigrid cycle, we are left with the choice of the smoothers, i.e., the iterators that improve the approximation of the solution on each of the P equations. A generic, explicit smoothing step on level p can be written as:

$$\mathbf{u}_p^{(n+1)} = \mathcal{Z}_p \mathbf{u}_p^{(n)} + \tilde{\mathcal{Z}}_p \mathbf{f}_p, \quad (\text{A.2})$$

where \mathcal{Z}_p and $\tilde{\mathcal{Z}}_p$ are two matrices acting on the previous guess and the forcing term, respectively, and their shape depends on the smoother chosen. Analogously, if we apply m_p smoothing steps, we obtain:

$$\mathbf{u}_p^{(n+m)} = \mathcal{Z}_{m,p} \mathbf{u}_p^{(n)} + \tilde{\mathcal{Z}}_{m,p} \mathbf{f}_p. \quad (\text{A.3})$$

In this work we consider explicit Runge-Kutta smoothers characterised by a polynomial $\mathcal{P}_S^N(x)$ and a time-step Δt , as in equation (18). In such case, the matrices from the previous equation are:

$$\mathcal{Z}_{m,p} = \left(\mathcal{P}_S^N(\Delta t \mathcal{A}_p) \right)^{m_p}, \quad \tilde{\mathcal{Z}}_{m,p} = \Delta t \left(\sum_{n=0}^{m_p-1} \left(\mathcal{P}_S^N(\Delta t \mathcal{A}_p) \right)^n \right) \tilde{\mathcal{P}}(\Delta t \mathcal{A}_p), \quad (\text{A.4})$$

where $\tilde{\mathcal{P}}(x) = (1 - \mathcal{P}_S^N(x))/x$ is obtained from the Runge-Kutta polynomial. Note that these operators directly apply m_p smoothing steps instead of just one. We further introduce the superscripts "do" and "up" for the solutions \mathbf{u}_p obtained in the down-cycle and the up-cycle and the subscript 0 or m_p to denote the solution vector before smoothing and after smoothing, respectively.

We now all the necessary components to write the multigrid operator as a single matrix. To do so, we start the *down-cycle* at the finest level with an initial guess $(\mathbf{u}_P)_0^{\text{do}}$, and apply the pre-smoothing steps. Then, the final residual is computed and restricted down to level $P-1$:

$$(\mathbf{u}_P)_{m_P}^{\text{do}} = \mathcal{Z}_{m,P} (\mathbf{u}_P)_0^{\text{do}}, \quad \mathbf{f}_{P-1} = \mathbf{R}_{P-1}^{P-1} (-\mathcal{A}_P) (\mathbf{u}_P)_{m_P}^{\text{do}}. \quad (\text{A.5})$$

The same procedure is applied iteratively to coarser levels, where the Correction Scheme requires the initial guess for the coarse level variables to be zero, $(\mathbf{u}_p)_0^{\text{do}} = \mathbf{0}$, $p = 0, \dots, P-1$. Hence, the smoothing steps in the down-cycle are expressed as follows:

$$(\mathbf{u}_p)_{m_p}^{\text{do}} = \tilde{\mathcal{Z}}_{m,p} \mathbf{f}_p. \quad (\text{A.6})$$

Combining the above equations and denoting I_p the $(p+1) \times (p+1)$ identity matrix, we obtain that the solutions at the coarse levels are linear in terms of the fine-level residual:

$$(\mathbf{u}_j)_{m_p}^{\text{do}} = \tilde{\mathcal{Z}}_{m,p} \left[\prod_{k=p+1}^{P-1} \mathbf{R}_k^{k-1} (I_k - \mathcal{A}_k \tilde{\mathcal{Z}}_{m,k}) \right] \mathbf{R}_p^{P-1} (-\mathcal{A}_p) (\mathbf{u}_p)_{m_p}^{\text{do}}, \quad p = P - 1, \dots, 0. \tag{A.7}$$

Once the down-cycle has completed, the up-cycle consists on the recursive application of two steps, going up from level $p = 0$ to level $p = P$. The first step is the prolongation of the solution from the coarser level $p - 1$ and its addition to the previously obtained solution at level p , effectively correcting it. Then, post-smoothing steps are applied at level p in the same way as in the down-cycle:

$$\begin{aligned} (\mathbf{u}_p)_0^{\text{up}} &= (\mathbf{u}_p)_{m_p}^{\text{do}} + \mathbf{R}_{p-1}^p (\mathbf{u}_{p-1})_{m_{p-1}}^{\text{up}} \\ (\mathbf{u}_p)_{m_p}^{\text{up}} &= \mathcal{Z}_{m,p} (\mathbf{u}_p)_0^{\text{up}} + \tilde{\mathcal{Z}}_{m,p} \mathbf{f}_p \end{aligned} \tag{A.8}$$

This can be expressed in a single step as:

$$(\mathbf{u}_p)_{m_p}^{\text{up}} = \mathcal{Z}_{m,p} \mathbf{R}_{p-1}^p (\mathbf{u}_{p-1})_{m_{p-1}}^{\text{up}} + \mathcal{Z}_{m,p} (\mathbf{u}_p)_{m_p}^{\text{do}} + \tilde{\mathcal{Z}}_{m,p} \mathbf{f}_p. \tag{A.9}$$

From the above we can infer that the up-cycle solutions are expressed in terms of the down-cycle solutions according to:

$$(\mathbf{u}_p)_{m_p}^{\text{up}} = \left(\prod_{l=0}^{p-1} \mathcal{Z}_{m,p-l} \mathbf{R}_{p-l-1}^{p-l} \right) (\mathbf{u}_0)_{m_0}^{\text{do}} + \sum_{k=1}^p \left[\left(\prod_{l=0}^{p-k-1} \mathcal{Z}_{m,p-l} \mathbf{R}_{p-l-1}^{p-l} \right) (\mathcal{Z}_{m,k} + I_k) (\mathbf{u}_k)_{m_k}^{\text{do}} \right]. \tag{A.10}$$

Equation (A.10) is only valid for $p < P$, since at the fine level the factor $(\mathcal{Z}_{m,p} + I_p)$ does not apply to $(\mathbf{u}_p)_{m_p}^{\text{do}}$, but only $\mathcal{Z}_{m,p}$. However, combining equation (A.10) with equation (A.7) we can express the solution vector $(\mathbf{u}_p)_{m_p}^{\text{up}}$ in terms of the initial guess $(\mathbf{u}_p)_0^{\text{do}}$. For instance, for $P = 1$, we obtain the multigrid matrix for a two-level V-cycle - the simplest possible:

$$(\mathbf{u}_1)_{m_1}^{\text{up}} = \mathcal{Z}_{m,1} \left\{ I_1 - \mathbf{R}_0^1 \tilde{\mathcal{Z}}_{m,0} \mathbf{R}_1^0 \mathcal{A}_1 \right\} \mathcal{Z}_{m,1} (\mathbf{u}_1)_0^{\text{do}}. \tag{A.11}$$

This is in agreement with existing results in the literature [103,93]. At this point we can express the multigrid operator as a single matrix for whichever polynomial order and number of smoothing steps.

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